

COMPOSITE MATERIALS FOR ELECTROMAGNETIC SAFETY**Lebedev V.,***Ph.D. in technical sciences, Assistant Professor, Assistant Professor of the department of plastics and biologically active polymers technology, National Technical University «Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute»***Miroshnichenko D.,***Doctor of Technical Sciences, professor, chair of the department of oil, gas and solid fuel refining technologies National Technical University «Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute»***Tykhomyrova T.,***Ph.D. in technical sciences, Assistant Professor, Assistant Professor of the department of Chemical Engineering and Environment Protection, National Technical University «Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute»***Kochetov M.***Ph.D. student of the department of Chemical Engineering and Environment Protection, National Technical University «Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute»*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7779041>**Abstract**

The purpose of the study is to researching of composite materials for electromagnetic safety. Polymer composites for electromagnetic radiation absorption based on polyamide 6 and silicon carbide were received in this study. It is shown that the optimal concentration of silicon carbide in the designed polymer composites from looking for their strength characteristics is 5 % mass It is shown that the spectrum transmission coefficient T of polymer composites is relatively the same in the entire frequency range, and the obtained standing wave ratio values indicate a rather large reflection coefficient Γ for the designed polymer composites.

Keywords: safety, composite, absorption, electromagnetic radiation, thermoplastic polymer, silicon carbide

Introduction

To provide IR radio-absorbing properties, it is necessary to introduce a dispersed conductive filler into its composition [1]. The main radio-physical characteristics value of a material with dispersed conductive phase is determined by the filler microstructure, particles size and its volume fraction in the polymer matrix [2, 15]. Different geometric shapes and sizes particles are used as a conductive filler. The particles shape are [3]: spherical (soot, metal powders, colloidal graphites, metallized microspheres), lamellar (expanded graphite, metal powders after attrition treatment, metallized mica) and needle-like (carbon fibers, metallized fibers, needles). As a rule, composites filled with lamellar or needle-like particles have better radio-absorbing characteristics [4]. Conductive filler type choice is determined by the composite complex dielectric permeability that depending on conductive filler concentration. At the same time, the concentration, taking into account the dispersity of the filler, should be optimized not only for achieving the reduction reflection coefficient required level, but also taking into account the weight, size, physical-mechanical and technological limitations in the RAM production and application [5].

The aim of the work is science-based technological solutions finding for receiving composite radio-absorbing materials with high electrophysical properties.

Raw materials and test methods

The objects of study were:

- Durethane polyamide 6 (Bayer, Germany);
- silicon carbide SiC.

Polymer composite materials were obtained by extruding pre-prepared raw materials in a single-screw laboratory extruder at a temperature of 170–200 °C and a roll rotation speed of 30–100 rpm.

The study of impact strength and breaking stress during bending of the samples of composite materials, without notching at a temperature 20 °C, was carried out on a pendulum head according to ISO 180 and ISO 178, respectively.

The measurement of the sample for transmission coefficient T (transmission T) and standing wave ratio (SWR) was carried out on an automated scalar spectrum analyzer P2-65 in the frequency range of 26–37.5 GHz. The spectrum was digitized and displayed on the computer screen using the National Instruments LabVIEW program. The sample completely filled the waveguide cross-section of 7.2 x 3.4 mm².

Results and discussion

Primary studies were aimed at studying the influence of silicon carbide particles the introduction on the polyamide 6 strength properties complex - figure 1.

Figure 1. Studying the influence of silicon carbide particles the introduction on the polyamide 6 strength properties complex

From the results shown in figure 1 it is seen that the modification of polyamide 6 with silicon carbide allows to obtain high-strength composite materials, while the optimal content of silicon carbide over 0.5 % by mass.

The spectrum transmission coefficient T of polymer composites based on polyamide 6 and 5 wt% silicon carbide, which is relatively the same throughout the frequency range is shown on fig. 2.

Figure 2.

Spectrum transmission coefficient T of polymer composites based on polyamide 6 and 5 % mass silicon carbide

The spectral dependence of the standing wave ratio on the SWR voltage of polymer composites based on polyamide 6 and 5 % mass silicon carbide is shown on fig. 3.

Figure 3. *Spectral dependence of the standing wave ratio on the SWR voltage of polymer composites based on polyamide 6 and 5 % mass silicon carbide*

The value of the calculated reflection coefficient Γ and absorption coefficient A of polymer composites based on polyamide 6 and 5 % mass silicon carbide is shown in fig. 3-4.

Figure 3. Spectral dependence of the calculated reflection coefficient Γ of polymer composites based on polyamide 6 and 5% mass silicon carbide

Figure 4. Spectral dependence of the calculated absorption coefficient A of polymer composites based on polyamide 6 and 5% mass silicon carbide

As a result of experimental data, it can be concluded that polymer composites based on polyamide 6 and 5% wt. silicon carbide are relatively transparent in the millimeter frequency range (about 3 dB, this is a 2-fold attenuation), which have a small value of the absorption coefficient.

Conclusion

Thus, polymer composites for electromagnetic radiation absorption based on polyamide 6 and silicon carbide were received in this study. It is shown that the optimal concentration of silicon carbide in the designed polymer composites from looking for their strength characteristics is 5% mass. It is shown that the spectrum transmission coefficient T of polymer composites is relatively the same in the entire frequency range, and the obtained SWR values indicate a rather large reflection coefficient Γ for the designed polymer composites.

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